

**"BLOOM'S TAXONOMY IN SECOND LANGUAGE ACQUISITION:
PROMOTING CRITICAL THINKING AND LEARNER AUTONOMY"**

Boydadayev Jakhongir Khamdamboyevich

English Language Teacher at Erkin Vokhidov Creativity School

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Abstract: The link between Bloom's Taxonomy, Second Language Acquisition (SLA), higher-order thinking abilities, learner autonomy, curriculum creation, assessment, language competency, and the role of the language instructor in education is examined in this article. The author contends that the application of Bloom's Taxonomy can help learners acquire higher-order thinking abilities and learner autonomy, which are necessary for reliable evaluations of language competency. The paper also emphasises the significance of incorporating critical thinking into curriculum development and language education. Overall, this article offers insightful information about the intricate relationships between language learning, cognitive development, and educational practise.

Keywords: Bloom's Taxonomy, Second Language Acquisition, critical thinking, learner autonomy, curriculum development, assessment, language proficiency, higher-order thinking skills, language teacher, education, accurate assessments, SLA.

**«ТАКСОНОМИЯ БЛУМА В ОСВОЕНИИ ВТОРОГО ЯЗЫКА: РАЗВИТИЕ
КРИТИЧЕСКОГО МЫШЛЕНИЯ И САМОСТОЯТЕЛЬНОСТИ УЧАЩИХСЯ»**

Аннотация: В этой статье рассматривается связь между таксономией Блума, овладением вторым языком (SLA), способностями мышления более высокого порядка, автономией учащихся, созданием учебных программ, оценкой, языковой компетенцией и ролью преподавателя языка в образовании. Автор утверждает, что применение Таксономии Блума может помочь учащимся приобрести мыслительные способности более высокого порядка и автономию учащегося, которые необходимы для надежной оценки языковой компетентности. В документе также подчеркивается важность включения критического мышления в разработку учебных программ и языковое образование. В целом, эта статья предлагает полезную информацию о сложных взаимосвязях между изучением языка, когнитивным развитием и образовательной практикой.

Ключевые слова: таксономия Блума, овладение вторым языком, критическое мышление, автономия учащегося, разработка учебной программы, оценка, знание языка, навыки мышления более высокого порядка, учитель языка, образование, точные оценки, SLA.

INTRODUCTION

Are you a language instructor wanting to create classes that support independent learning and higher-order thinking skills? Bloom's Taxonomy is the only resource you need. Benjamin Bloom created this framework in 1956, and it has been extensively applied in education to direct curriculum creation and evaluation. In this article, we'll look at how Bloom's Taxonomy may be used in the study of second language acquisition (SLA) to foster the development of critical thinking abilities, learner autonomy, and more precise language competence evaluations.

A system called Bloom's Taxonomy divides learning objectives into six categories, from lower-order thinking skills to higher-order thinking skills. Benjamin Bloom created the taxonomy in 1956, and it has since been extensively utilised in education to direct curriculum creation and assessment.

In the area of second language acquisition (SLA), there has been a growing interest in using Bloom's Taxonomy. This is because the framework offers language teachers a helpful road map for creating classes that encourage the development of higher-order cognitive abilities, which are crucial for language learning.

The Bloom's Taxonomy is a useful tool for both educators and students. This framework offers a precise framework for developing and evaluating learning objectives while promoting critical thinking and higher-order thinking abilities. Using Bloom's Taxonomy has many advantages, including the ability to identify and prioritise learning goals, align instructional strategies and assessments, support differentiation and personalization of instruction, promote active and engaged learning, develop metacognitive skills and self-regulated learning strategies, encourage collaboration and communication among learners, provide a common language for discussing teaching and learning, and ensure that learners are engaged in their studies.

Using Bloom's Taxonomy allows teachers to develop a more student-centered approach to learning, which is one of its most important advantages. The emphasis on critical thinking and higher-order thinking abilities encourages students to participate actively in their own education. This strategy encourages learners to be innovative and creative by offering a framework for creating tests that measure various cognitive abilities.

Bloom's Taxonomy encourages active and engaged learning while also assisting students in gaining a better comprehension of concepts and ideas. Learners are better able to draw connections between various fields of knowledge and apply their learning to novel circumstances when a framework for curriculum creation and instructional materials that are in line with learning objectives and evaluation is provided. This method also promotes the growth of analytical and problem-solving abilities, empowering students to spot areas of comprehension that still require improvement.

The use of Bloom's Taxonomy also encourages the development of abilities for lifelong learning. This framework aids in building a community of learners who are dedicated to continual growth and development by fostering cooperation and communication among them. Additionally, it gives educators a common vocabulary to talk about teaching and learning, allowing them to exchange best practises and work together on teaching methods.

Bloom's Taxonomy should be used in current SLA mostly to foster critical thinking abilities. To generate opinions or make decisions, critical thinking entails assessing, analysing, and synthesising information. Language learners need to be able to grasp and analyse complicated texts, express their thoughts, and participate in meaningful conversations, therefore these abilities are crucial.

Language instructors can create classes that encourage critical thinking abilities by using Bloom's Taxonomy. For instance, instructors might concentrate on improving their students' capacity to retain and comprehend vocabulary words and grammar rules at the lowest levels of the taxonomy. At more advanced levels, teachers might push students to analyse challenging materials, assess arguments, and apply their knowledge to practical situations.

The promotion of student autonomy is another reason why Bloom's Taxonomy should be used in contemporary SLA. The ability of learners to direct their own learning is referred to as learner autonomy. Language teachers may assist students to become more independent and self-directed in their study by encouraging higher-order thinking abilities.

For instance, teachers might create exercises that require students to define their own objectives, devise their own learning techniques, and assess their own development at the higher

levels of the taxonomy. This method encourages learner autonomy while also assisting students in acquiring metacognitive abilities, which are crucial for lifetime learning.

Lastly, using Bloom's Taxonomy in contemporary SLA can assist instructors in creating tests that gauge higher-order thinking abilities. Traditional language tests frequently emphasise memory and recall, which are examples of lower-order cognitive abilities. These abilities, however, may not always represent a learner's capacity to utilise language in authentic contexts.

Language teachers may create tests that gauge higher-order thinking abilities like analysis, evaluation, and synthesis by utilising Bloom's Taxonomy. This method helps teachers pinpoint areas where learners need further attention and gives a more accurate depiction of learners' language skills.

In conclusion, incorporating Bloom's Taxonomy into contemporary SLA is crucial for fostering critical thinking abilities, learner autonomy, and creating tests that assess higher-order thinking abilities. Using this framework, language instructors may create classes that encourage meaningful learning experiences and aid students in acquiring the abilities necessary to thrive in the globalised world of today. This framework offers a precise framework for developing and evaluating learning objectives, fostering critical thinking and higher-order thinking abilities, and fostering active and engaged learning. Additionally, it stimulates cooperation and communication among students, supports the growth of metacognitive abilities and self-regulated learning techniques, and makes sure that learning is significant, applicable, and transferrable to real-world situations. Bloom's Taxonomy may be used by educators to construct a more student-centered learning strategy that encourages the acquisition of lifetime learning abilities and equips students for success in the twenty-first century.

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